

ABOUT DESIGN DEFINITION AND LANDSCAPE DESIGN STYLES

Allambergenova Arzayim Qudaybergenova

Karakalpak State University named after Berdak.

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Abstract. This article provides information on the definition of design and styles of landscape design, the history of the origin and styles.

Keywords: design, landscape, style, composition, art.

О ДИЗАЙНЕ И СТИЛЯХ ЛАНДШАФТНОГО ДИЗАЙНА

Аннотация. В статье дана информация об определении дизайна и стилях ландшафтного дизайна, истории возникновения и стилях.

Ключевые слова: дизайн, ландшафт, стиль, композиция, искусство.

Translated from the Italian language, the word "design" means "concept", "composition", "model". In Russian, it appeared recently, but the art itself began to take shape many centuries ago.

A modern specialist engaged in the type of activity in question must know many features from the scientific fields and be able to use them correctly in practice when creating projects. The masters of their work work in cooperation with architects, clients, builders, suppliers and contractors to organize the interior space.

In the middle of the 19th century, the development of industrial production created a need for a new type of activity focused on decoration and aesthetics. That's how the design came about.

At the end of the 19th century, the main rules of theory and principles were formed, which later influenced the schools of masters. Thus design began to combine art and craft. At the beginning of the 20th century, artists rose in art. They developed the corporate identity of the enterprises and were able to influence the production of various electrical appliances and automobiles. Thus, design became an art-industrial activity. The appearance of the graduate is related to the formation of design schools in the 20th century.

The formation of this art in Russia has a periodic character: a high growth was followed by a low decline. But power has always been and will always be aesthetic. The development of the design can be divided into several stages.

In the first stage (1917-1922), the creation of design was carried out in the collision of production with the art of mass propaganda, as well as in the active design of streets, holidays and political marches. During this period, new approaches to the design of advertising, poster and book products began to be used, which marked the beginning of the development of graphic design.

In the second stage (1923-1932) it became one of the main centers of training of professional designers in Russian production faculties. At this time, certain concepts directed to the further development of art were formed, and projects for the arrangement of homes, workplaces, and public spaces began to be developed. Won in collages, type compositions, book designs, poster graphics.

When organizing a space in various stylistic decisions, you should consider not only the main objects, but also your details. Experts recommend that you first develop a plan for yourself, for example, to determine where the tracks will be located, an open space, a place for recreation,

a pond, etc. Landscape design styles of suburban areas solve this problem in different ways, taking into account practical aspects and priorities.

Focus on important things and elements: Plants are recommended to be planted in groups, so you can create colorful compositions that change throughout the year. It is important to balance the elements of the structure. Landscape design styles include many details that can be divided into groups. The central object is the building and the task for it, which makes it fully compatible with the house.

For the design of the site, it is customary to use English, forest and lawn, which can be equal to the ground. Each option is suitable for different styles. During the registration process, landscaping of the garden is carried out, it should be designed so that the garden changes throughout the year and does not lose its originality. If possible, designers recommend organizing an artificial water body on the site, for example, a pond, pond, waterfall, etc. Depending on the chosen design direction, the selected landscape decoration is of great importance. For example, there can be statues, pots, mountain tops, etc.

When choosing landscape design styles, designers often combine several directions and different techniques. As a result, you will find a harmonious site and include the most interesting design ideas. In this case, the design is carried out without taking into account the features of the landscape. This direction is usually called eclecticism.

Its main features:

When working on the site, you should use at least 2-3 styles. There are contrasts, but for their combination it is customary to pay attention to a common or colorful, for example. Functional zones should be separated and they should have clear boundaries. For this, you can choose arches, columns, etc. It should be noted that each zone has its own style, which makes the site original. It is not recommended to use too many elements in the design, because it creates the effect of complexity.

It is not good to install furniture, walls and decor in one color. This causes all parts to become one.

Alpine style in landscape design. This option is perfect for occupying mountain-like places.

At ground level, you can arrange a stone bank or a mountain top. Landscaping in front of the house in a modern style and behind it means using a lot of stones, and you can also include ceramics and metal in the design. Another characteristic feature is conflicts. Zoning is possible, but all parts of the site must be integrated. The house should be on a hill. The general color scheme is light, but there are many bright additions. All styles of landscape design have their own characteristics in plants, and such choices are needed in the direction of the foothills: hardy and fragile fruit crops. Such trees are recommended: honas, gooseberry, raspberry, hydrangea, olive and the like. Flowers can be different, so even a simple wormwood looks great.

Regular style in landscape design. The distinctive features of this direction include symmetry, regular geometric shapes and order. Regular French style for large areas only. Its basic concept is that human nature prevails and requires order from the basic chaos. Axial compositions formed around the main objects are very popular.

An integral part of the garden is the bosquet. The regular style of landscape design has its own characteristics: the right lawn, sculptures, discounts and many paths. Plants should not cover the edges, so you can plant annuals and bulbs. Firs, thuja and trees that can be cut are suitable.

Landscape design, which should be symmetrical and have clear edges, is actively used in the hygienic regular style. Garden furniture can be stone or wood, the main one looks luxurious.

English style in landscape design

This direction is characterized by naturalness, lack of strict forms and merging with the surrounding nature. Most garden equipment for landscape design is subject to serious changes, and English (landscape) - small, even some carelessness and primitiveness are allowed. Can be selected for small areas. The presence of winding roads made of natural stones, natural water bodies and well-kept lawns are the main features. It is customary to install gazebos and benches in convenient places on the site. The remaining zone can be separated by a cage or an arch. Like multi-level flower beds in the English style. If you want to install sculptures, you do not need to place them in the center of the composition, and you need to place them in arbitrary places of correct solutions.

The design uses a vertical landscape and many colors, such as tulips, mallow, etc. In addition, you can plant pumpkins, pumpkins and juniper plants, and the trees should be tall and shady.

Middle style in landscape design. This is one of the most difficult ways to implement directions, as it combines citrus and coniferous plants, as well as beautiful ponds. Medium standards are ideal for light areas. For a harsh climate, you should get analogues of subtropical plants. The main styles of landscape design include the Mediterranean direction, and there are characteristic features similar to it: many colors and greens, many natural stones, wooden benches, and garden forms. , pools, cascades and fountains.

Japanese style in landscape design. In this direction, it is customary to pay attention to details, because each element has a meaning. The main details are rock, water and plants. The Japanese style in the landscape means the balance of all components, the color scale is limited, and the main elements are stones and plants. The main plantations include pine, crown, decorative apple trees, plum and hill-shaped rock. For a change, you can plant pot, corn, peony and iris. The main elements of the decor: a garden of stones, a gazebo and dry streams. A water source is required.

Landscape design styles. This is the most popular design trend based on simplicity, naturalness and ease. The state style in the style of landscape design implies the rejection of fixed lines and the reference point to the freedom of creativity. It is suitable for all places and characteristics: the presence of bright colors and natural materials, for feeding traditionally used fruit trees and bushes, as well as curly and medicinal plants. For decoration, you can install wells, fences, benches, barrels, magazines and various figures.

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